

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ВРЕМЕННОЙ КАТЕГОРИИ В НЕМЕЦКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

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THE SIGNIFICANCE OF TENSE CATEGORY IN GERMAN LANGUAGE

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Тематика представленной автором статьи - одна из важнейших тем современного немецкого языкознания, которая всегда находится в центре внимания ученых. Лингвистические факты подтверждают, что формы времени не только выполняют грамматическую функцию. Хотя категория времени является широкой темой в немецкой и азербайджанской лингвистике, автор кратко рассмотрел грамматико-лексическое поле темпоральности и систематизировал основные средства выражения, прокомментировал элементы выражения с разных языковых уровней для достижения этого значения. является одной из самых важных и определяющих грамматических категорий глагола. Благодаря наличию этих грамматических особенностей, характерных системных связей, глагол, благодаря своему парадигматическому объему, образует широкие и всеобъемлющие грамматические формы, несравнимые с любой другой частью речи. По мнению автора, глагол считается самой важной и богатой частью речи с грамматической точки зрения. Одним из основных моментов статьи является сравнение понятия грамматического времени с азербайджанским и английским языками и описание функционально-смысловых пространств времени. Изучение распределения данных средств выражения в этих функционально-семантических областях, интенсивности их распределения представляется очень важным с точки зрения изучения точек выражения каждого из этих средств, а также эффекта транспозиции временных форм. в целом. На приведенных примерах автор доказывает, что отношения между предметным и грамматическим временами чрезвычайно сложны и красочны, тесно взаимосвязаны и взаимосвязаны.

ABSTRACT

The topic of the article presented by the author is one of the most important topics in modern German linguistics. Linguistic facts confirm that time forms do not only have a grammatical function. Although the category of time is a broad topic in German and Azerbaijani linguistics, the author briefly reviewed the grammatical-lexical field of temporalism and systematized the main means of expression, commented on the elements of expression from different language levels to achieve this meaning. category is one of the most important and defining grammatical categories of the verb. Due to the existence of these grammatical features, characteristic system connections, the verb, due to its paradigmatic volume, forms a wide and comprehensive grammatical forms incomparable to any other part of speech. According to the author, the verb is considered the most important and richest part of speech from the grammatical point of view. One of the highlights of the article is the comparison of the concept of grammatical tense with the Azerbaijani and English languages and the description of time-functional-semantic areas. The study of the distribution of the given means of expression in those functional-semantic areas, the intensity of their distribution seems to be very important in terms of studying the expression points of each of these means, as well as the transposition effect of time forms as a whole.

With the examples given, the author proves that the relations between objective and grammatical tenses are extremely complex and colorful, and are closely interconnected and interconnected.

Ключевые слова: глагол, грамматика, языкознание, сказуемое, настоящее время, временный характер, формы времени, аффективный глагол, союз, будущее время.

Keywords: Verb, grammer, linguistics, predicate, the present, forms of Verbs, the effective Verbs, conjunction, Future.

As is known, the tense category is one of the most important and defining grammatical categories of the verb. This grammatical category is so important and characteristic for the verb system that German linguistics uses the term verb (time-denoting word) along with the verb. Thus, the verb is first and foremost understood as a part of speech that expresses the concept of time. It is also known that the categories of person, quantity, tense, form and type give the complete and comprehensive grammatical characteristics of the verb. Due to the

existence of these grammatical signs and characteristic system relations, the verb forms grammatical forms that are so wide and comprehensive that they cannot be compared with any other part of speech due to its paradigmatic volume. It is noted in the linguistics literature that active verbs have 177 word forms, and intransitive verbs have 91 word forms. [2]

Thus, the verb takes different forms according to three persons, two quantitative categorical forms, six tense forms, three image varieties, two (according to

some sources three) types of affiliation, it is divided according to Participle I and Participle II, Infinitive I and Infinitive II grammatical forms. It is no coincidence that the verb is considered the most important and richest part of speech from a grammatical point of view. If the noun is in the first position from the semantic point of view, the verb moves to the front position due to grammatical changes and dynamics.

To explain the category of grammatical time, it is necessary to distinguish the logical-philosophical and purely grammatical meanings of time. The terms "objective tense" and "grammatical tense" are usually used here. Objective time exists independently of human consciousness and includes three times - past, present and future. The famous Azerbaijani linguist A. Akhundov explains and interprets the concept of grammatical time as follows: "Grammatical time is the expression in language of the time that exists in the objective world independent of us in human thinking. Grammar does not create time by itself, it only marks the objective time reflected in the human mind with its special formal signs in the language, and at the same time makes it much more concrete" [1]

In the logical-philosophical sense, the following signs of time, in other words, objective time, are noted: time is irreversible - it continues in only one direction and is never subjected to returns or reversals, it is constantly flowing and moving; time is infinite - it has no beginning and no end. Thus, objective time covers three time levels: past time - present time - future time. As you can see, these time measurements are quite common and widespread, and taking them within relatively precise boundaries creates considerable difficulties. Grammatical time forms perform the function of overcoming these difficulties, clarifying and concretizing the dimensions of time, and demarcating a certain and specific time period. It is not accidental that different time forms of different numbers and functions are formed in different languages of the world to express those time steps. If the modern German language has six tenses of the news form, 13 tenses of the verb are noted in modern English (4 past, 4 present, 5 future tenses) (A. Akhundov, 5). A. N. Kononov draws attention to the existence of 15 tense forms in the modern Turkish language in his work "Grammatik's of modern Turkish literary language" [4]

The invariance of time degrees and the variability of grammatical time forms in different systematic languages confirm the expression of the concept of time in different forms in different peoples' language consciousness, thus the uniqueness of grammatical time, national-subjective character. This shows that the specification and concretization by time in all three time periods in different languages confirms once again that the internal rules of each language, language consciousness, the perception of objective time in human thinking are manifested in a different, or rather, unique way.

Innumerable actions, situations, work, cases, intervals of change of state, etc. how are they differentiated by time, how are the time steps demarcated, how are different transitions and change states sequenced with each other, and what is the starting point, time naming, and determination criteria used here? These

questions have made scientists think a lot from time to time. [6]

In the linguistic literature, speaking time is taken as the starting point for determining tenses. If the work, situation, action falls before the speaking time, past tense; present tense if the work, situation, action falls at the same time or relatively at the same time as the time of conversation; If the work, situation, action is after the time of conversation, it is expressed in the future tense. Differentiation and differentiation within each time stage is possible not only with the variety of time forms and grammatical time signs, but also with the help of other language means of expressing time, especially lexical means of time concept.

If only grammatical tense forms were used to express different time units, in other words, if each objective time difference had a separate tense form, language could not perform its generalizing function, communication could not exist. Thus, the non-grammatical means of the concept of time are important in the communication process in order to clarify, specify and delimit the facts of the present time, which are especially broad, endless time stages, past and future time, as well as relatively concrete and visible (in other words, closer to the concept of speaking time). plays a role. Compare:

- 1) Vor Millionen Jahren sah die Welt ganz anders aus.
- 2) Gestern fühlte er sich unwohl.
- 3) Heute sah er sehr traurig aus.
- 4) Morgen fahre ich nach München.
- 5) Er ist immer gesund und munter. [3]

Past time, present time, future time global time stages are sometimes expressed in a general and simplified way with gestern-heute-morgen coordinates. However, this global time characteristic also does not fully and honestly express the colorful and multi-level perceptions of time, and serves only as a benchmark, a benchmark for comparison. The semantic volume of the word "Today" is not at all

Equal to the concept of speaking time, speaking moment, and cannot be fully covered. Here, at least, it is necessary to distinguish the semantic distinctions of the near present, the relatively near present, the "past" present, the absolute present, continuous, continuous, prospective present. In this case, it is not always possible to use the Präsens tense. Gegenwart- Präsens balance is disturbed. For example, if the time characteristic of a work, situation, action, its specific time intensity is clarified and concretized, other clarifying and concretizing means, along with the time adverb, gain real content and importance. Within the word Heute, it is possible to place the most diverse, both quantitatively and qualitatively, time-intervals and the facts of the work, situation, and action happening here within a certain time distance (24 hours). Heute früh, heute am Morgen, kurz vor dem Frühstück, nach dem Abendbrot, während der Mittagspause, nach dem Mittagessen, am Nachmittag, heute um zehn Uhr, heute abend, etc. Such time distinctions, especially regarding past and future time stages, can be extended indefinitely. However, the language takes the path of generalization and uses irrel-

evant, unimportant, unnecessary facts for communication, as well as extreme and unnecessary time characteristics. [5]

Let's consider examples:

1) In Südamerika leben noch heutzutage giftige Schlangen.

2) Das Baby schläft.

3) Die Erde ist rund.

4) Monika lebt in Berlin.

5) Es blitzt.

6) Er ruft sie immer vor dem Abendessen an.

7) Solche Menschen sind in der Regel freundlich.

8) Nach dem Tod seines Vaters sieht er sehr traurig und besorgt aus.

9) Sein Vater arbeitet als Lehrer, und seine Mutter ist eine vorbildliche Hausfrau.

Example (1) hides the idea that venomous snakes have lived and will live in South America in the past, now, and at least in the near future. Current information is that this presence continues today and in the present, and that it is or may be dangerous to human life. Thus, the real fact essentially includes both past, present and future time stages and takes on a general, repeated character. We are talking about the general time characteristics of poisonous snakes living in South America. Thus, in that form, the following meaning components are expressed in a joint way:

- Relevance at the time of conversation;
- belonging to the past and future times;
- Generality of movement characteristics;
- Element of meaning of continuity, repetition;
- Determination of a certain fact of reality; [4]

In sentence (2), we are not talking about the generality of the global time, but about the "detailing" of a specific, recent time period, differentiation and continuity. When the child's sleep time starts and how long it will last is perceived by visible contours at a distance of time that can be determined by biological laws. The work is not only relevant for the talk time, but it is displayed in the time intervals of the whole day or a certain period of the day. It can be said that various components of meaning are expressed in such an expression:

- referring to the time of conversation in the present tense;
- Partial compatibility of talk time and work;
- belonging to the past and future times (within the concrete present time frame);
- Continuity of work, relative continuity, [8]

In sentence (3), we are talking about mentioning a real, proven, proven fact. It is shown that the Earth was spherical in the past, in the present, and probably in the future. The fact that the Earth is spherical is presented as a fact of timelessness. Thus, these meaning components are expressed in that sentence:

- Relevance at the time of the conversation, not belonging to the moment of the speech,
- Generality, mention as a specific fact or event,
- belonging to the past and future time stages,
- The continuity and repetition of a certain sign, giving without interruption,

Sentence (4) expresses the concept of evaluating various facts and probabilities about where a girl named Monika lives. Monika has lived, lives and will live in

Berlin before, now and probably in the near future. Thus, it combines the elements of meaning:

- belonging to the present time, specific relevance,
- spreading over the past and future times, not belonging to those time stages,
- Continuation of the verb sign, verbal characteristic,
- The reality of repeatability and potential continuity [7]

As can be seen from the examples, example (5) expresses the classic present tense meaning. It is talked about as soon as the lightning strikes. The fact of time lapse is only the short time distance caused by the lightning flash reaching the ground.

In the sentence (6) it occurs at the same time as the moment of speaking, spreading over the past and future time, the immutability and stability of the qualitative characteristics of the action, (7)- falling into the same time as the moment of speaking, belonging to the past and future tenses, the realization of the meaning of possibility ; (8)- the fact that the case, the situation falls at the same time as the time of conversation, the relevance covers a longer period of time, the continuity of the verb sign; (9)- continuity and continuity of the work, the situation coincides with the time of conversation, the work starts in the past time to a large extent and will probably continue in the future time stage.

The cited examples prove that the relationship between the objective and grammatical tenses is extremely complex and colorful, and is connected by close interaction and transitions. They often do not correspond to each other; manifest themselves in the form of invariant semantic meanings and the diversity of their linguistic expression.

Tense forms, that is, the system of morphological comparisons, form the center of the functional (grammatical-lexical) time domain, the dominant means of expression. Grammatical tenses express the meaning of time unambiguously, constitute the most specialized, grammatical zed type of expression of that meaning and are used regularly. Those tenses are those that occur in the past, present and future tenses, that is, before and after the time of speaking, in progress or from the time of speaking. Refers to the work, situation and actions that happened later to the relevant time stages, and acts as the main expression forms of differential-semantic meanings related to those time perspectives. In the literature of linguistics, tense forms are divided into absolute and relative tense forms. Präsens, Imperfekt and the first form of the future tense (Futurum I) are called absolute, and Perfekt, Plusquamperfekt and the second form of the future tense (Futurum II) are called relative tense forms. The processing of the perfect tense as both an absolute and a relative tense is noted separately. The well-known linguist E. I. Shendel's famous triangle of tenses clearly expresses this [7]

Thus, the classification of time forms fully corresponds not only to their meaning structure, but also to their working moments and functionality.

The expression of categorical time meaning does not end only with tense forms. If this were the case, it would only be about the grammatical time category. If

we examine the concept of temporality as a broad functional-semantic field, we will witness that the means of expression mentioned below are also grouped around the invariant-semantic time meaning. Thus, the time-functional-semantic field can be imagined as follows:

1) system of morphological contrasts - six known tense forms of the verb (Präsens, Präteritum, Perfekt, Plusquamperfekt, Futurum I, Futurum II);

2) time perspectives of noun forms of the verb (Nominativformen des Verbs) (das weinende Kind, der geschriebene Roman); Er ging an mir vorbei, ohne mich begrüßt zu haben;

3) Adverbs like heute, vorgestern, morgen, übermorgen, which express the meaning of time and act as time adverbs in the sentence;

4) Temporal meaning nouns used with and without prepositions (die Woche, vor dem Abendessen, das Jahrhundert);

5) Conjunctions that express time relations within subordinate complex sentences (nachdem, als, wenn, sobald, etc.);

6) Adjectives expressing time meaning, giving different time characteristics of nouns, defining them by time (gegenwärtig, vergangen, gestig, heutig, etc.);

7) Time-meaning prepositions (bis, während, seit);

8) Question words expressing different temporal relations, used to get information about time or clarify it (wann, seit wann, bis wann, wie oft, wie lange);

9) nie, niemals, nimmer, nie und nimmer\ nie und nimmermehr-type expressive tense emotive words;

10) bald-bald coordinating conjunction (in subordination);

11) conjunctive forms expressing implicit (hidden, non-obvious) time (Wenn ich es gewusst hätte, so hätte ich ihn geholfen);

12) Verbs characterizing work, state, movement and situation by time: dauern, anhalten, tagen, vergehen, pausieren, etc. [6]

As it can be seen, the meaning of time is expressed not only by grammatical zed expression forms - time measures (morphological level unit) but also by lexical, semantic, lexical-semantic, lexical-phraseological means representing the most diverse language levels. Tense forms enter into colorful semantic-syntactic relations within the interrelated text, penetrate into neighboring fields and enter into multi-sided synonymy and polysemy relationships, acquire certain stylistic possibilities.

Regarding the horizontal structure of the field of functional-semantic temporality, it should be characterized as these micro fields:

1). Current time micro field

2). Past tense micro field

3). Future time micro field

It seems very important to study the distribution of the mentioned means of expression on those functional-semantic fields, the intensity of distribution, either from the point of view of investigating the expression points of each of those means, or the transposition effect of tense forms as a whole. [5]

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